

Botanical villages, an initiative in favour of local flora

Authors

Clara Pladevall Izard¹; Meritxell Dalmau Miarnau¹; Maria Martín²; Isalina Payré²

¹ Andorra Recerca + Innovació, Avda. Rocafort 21-23, Ed. Molí 3r, AD600, Sant Julià de Lòria, Principat d'Andorra

² Fédération des Réserves Naturelles Catalanes, Rue de Mahou 9, 66500, Prades, France

Abstract

Floralab+ is an Interreg POCTEFA project entitled *Shared Strategy and Tools for the Flora of the Eastern Pyrenees* directed by the French *Fédération des Réserves Naturelles Catalanes*. The partners of the project are proposing an innovation strategy for the study, preservation and dissemination of the flora of the Pyrenees. One of the actions considered in the project is the development, promotion and management of the future accreditation of the *Pyrenean Botanical Villages*, a label intended for municipalities that aims to support and promote initiatives to consider local flora in territorial policies. The project has a very specific roadmap to achieve the proposed objectives, all done with strict harmony between all the partners involved and regarding the cross-border nature of the project. At this moment, in May 2025, the network is working on interviews with the first interested villages' selection and on the accreditation methodology. This is research in process projects that must be flexible to the inputs received by different partners and would be in the future. The development of the future label is still in progress, and all the cross-border network is working on it.

Key words

Villages, flora, botany, Pyrenees, accreditation, cross-border cooperation.

The members of the Interreg POCTEFA Floralab+ are working on the development of a cross-border accreditation that will promote territorial and participatory approaches in favor of the conservation and promotion of local botanical heritage.

Introduction

Floralab+ is a project that proposes a cross-border strategy focused on the study, conservation and knowledge of the Pyrenean flora within the framework of an Interreg POCTEFA - a European cross-border cooperation program created to promote the sustainable development of the border territory of Spain, France and Andorra (POCTEFA, n.d.). The project, officially titled “Estrategia y herramientas compartidas a favor de la flora del este del Pirineo” - *Shared Strategy and Tools for the Flora of the Eastern Pyrenees* and led by the *Fédération des Réserves Naturelles Catalanes*, is separated into two axes. The first one is centered on those territories with an exceptional botanical biodiversity. The *Open-air laboratories* are created in these territories, with the aim of becoming a reference point in terms of scientific and technical knowledge. The second axis, the object of this paper, in contrast to the first, is focused on the important role of the village citizens in the conservation of flora. It is known by scientists and researchers the importance and the richness of the Pyrenees botanical heritage (there are currently up to 3,600 known species of different vascular flora). However, few local authorities embrace this issue, and even fewer raise awareness among citizens. For that, this innovation action proposes a cross-border tool for citizen appropriation of the environment and flora biodiversity. So, the axis has the aim to develop, promote and manage the future accreditation of the *Pyrenean Botanical Villages*, a label that pretends to support and promote local initiatives in favor of the local flora in territorial policies of the cross-border territory of the eastern Pyrenees. Thus, it will highlight the municipalities that are working (or wishing to work) to promote local botanical heritage, both from the perspective of improving knowledge and conservation, but also, and above all, from the perspective of disseminating and raising public awareness about this exceptional heritage. The creation of this label was started within the also POCTEFA project named Floralab (2020-2022), based on an initial pilot experience in a town in Ripollès, Catalunya. Now, with the Floralab+ project, it is the moment of openness and pushing this dynamic to a cross-border dimension. In addition to these two axes, but always related, the project also plans to produce training and awareness-raising tools dedicated to the plants of the Pyrenees. To serve the different axes of the project, various innovative and cross-cutting educational resources will be created. Scientific innovation, territorial involvement, and strong synergies with other Pyrenean approaches and networks will form the foundation of Floralab+, for a better understanding of Pyrenean botanical issues by society.

More specifically, the principal objective of this second axis is to give a cross-border impetus to the accreditation of the *Pyrenean Botanical Villages*, primarily aimed at candidate villages in the east of the Pyrenees, that will promote territorial policies and participatory approaches in favor of the conservation and promotion of local botanical heritage. Thus, this label highlights the villages that work for the local botanical heritage through citizen involvement: considering and improving local botanical knowledge, carrying out participatory restoration initiatives, and disseminating the Pyrenean botanical richness to the public (for example, botanical gardens, local and signpost trails, events, and school projects).

For all the reasons explained above, Action 4 of the Floralab+ project is focused solely on the cross-border creation and development of the accreditation, an action led by a Spanish partner of the project, IBB-CSIC. However, action is co-built by a network of partners that will constantly support each other in carrying out all the activities and coordinating initiatives, bringing the long-awaited cross-border dimension to the label. Nevertheless, all the activities will be locally directed by local institutions. For example, Andorra Recerca + Innovació is one of the partners of the POCTEFA project, and its objective is to implement the project within Andorra and, at the same time, act as a driving force and reference for other Andorran entities that could host some of the proposed. Other project partners are the FNRC and the PNR-PC working in the Pyrénées-Orientales, the CEN-ANA in the Ariège, the IBB-CSIC and the Catalan natural park partners, led by the Generalitat de Catalunya. It is important to highlight that all towns interested in obtaining the label will receive strong support at all levels (governance, scientific, technical and logistical aspects) from the project's social structures presented above.

This action encompasses, at the same time, three different activities. First, the first activity pretends to be the starting point of the cross-border accreditation process, that is, it aims to create the monitoring and support structure for the dynamics of governance, development and implementation of the action plans of the candidate villages. The process will be based on several exchanges, and together (town councils, villagers, landowners, tourism agents, etc.) must work to reach an agreement and validate a future action plan (a detailed document with all the planned actions). Secondly, the second action will work on scientific and participatory support for the conservation of local flora in the villages. It means that the project network will support all the most scientific challenges in these villages (botanical inventories, making cartography, etc.). However, it is expected that progressively the villages can become more independent and self-sustaining thanks to the commitment of local people, who are sensitized and trained in these challenges. Finally, the last action is focused on the possible communication and awareness activities about the Pyrenean botanical heritage aimed at the citizens of the

villages, taking advantage of the high diversity of flora that can be found around the same villages and along local trails. For example, some ideas could be the creation of complementary botanical trails within the project area, the creation or enhancement of botanical gardens, and the implementation of educational projects for local schools.

The initiative of the *Pyrenean Botanical Villages* should be understood as an innovative and experimental proposal resulting from cross-border collaboration between Spain, France, and Andorra, as well as from regional efforts (POCTEFA, n.d.). In addition, the POCTEFA Programs promote the sustainable development of innovative projects that aim to improve the quality of life for local inhabitants by developing, for example, new products and services (Andorra Living Lab, n.d.). Moreover, the active participation of local citizens, environmental stakeholders, and the commitment of political leaders is noteworthy, aligning well with the principles of the Living Labs approach (Andorra Living Lab, n.d.; Gascó, 2017; Veeckman & Temmerman, 2021). Therefore, the accreditation of these Pyrenean villages substantially fulfils the key criteria of recognized Living Labs.

Methodology

Project partners and villages interested in accreditation

The POCTEFA project is led by the *Fédération des Réserves Naturelles Catalanes*, however, the specific action of creating the label of *Pyrenees Botanical Villages* is carried out by the IBB-CSIC in close contact with the rest of the partners of the cross-border network. Therefore, the territories integrated in the project are those that are in the work areas of the institutions mentioned. For the moment, the interested villages are principally on the French side of the Pyrenees, as Eyne, Mantet, Py, Nohèdes, Conat, Llo, Angoustrine, Saillagouse, Arboussols and Montségur, and at the Catalan side the network is working with Sant Feliu de Pallerols, Setcases and probably other villages as Tuixent and Araós. Specifically, in Andorra the interested towns are Ordino, La Massana and Encamp (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map with the location of the candidate villages (purple) and the pilot village (red) for obtaining the accreditation of Pyrenees Botanical Villages.

Action procedure

The project has a very specific roadmap to achieve the proposed objectives, always in harmony with the results obtained during the pilot test carried out in the village of Setcases, in the Ripollès region of Catalonia, included in the previous project of Floralab (see the Results and Discussion section). First, it is intended to work on interviews with interested villages. A group of the *Fédération des Réserves Naturelles Catalanes* is working in some of them with the villages mentioned above. In these interviews, they are trying to discover the objectives and the expectations of the villages interested in the accreditation (see the Results and Discussion section). In addition, we are starting to work with the methodology of accreditation based on the document that dealt with this topic, written based on the experience of Setcases during 2020 and 2022 (Tenas & Oliver, 2022). In the coming months, the project partners will work together on the development of a newly proposed methodology for the certification of the *Botanical Villages*. After that, it is planned to formally present it to the interested municipalities, and begin working on the approach to short, medium and long-term action plans for each town. Subsequently, the villages, with the help of the network, will be able to begin working with the proposed actions. Finally, it is important to always consider the temporal planning of future actions and work to ensure financing in line with the objectives proposed.

Results and Discussion

At present, there are no concrete results regarding the implementation of this action within the project. The development of the future *Pyrenees Botanical Villages* is still in progress,

and it is too early to report outcomes. However, it is worth highlighting the results obtained during the pilot test carried out in the village of Setcases. A key component of the pilot initiative was the creation of a local flora guide. This initiative was carried out by the newly formed «Grup de Flora de Setcases», comprising approximately 30 local participants. The group engaged in four botanical outings, during which they collected approximately 400 photographs of native plant species. These images were used to illustrate seven proposed botanical routes designed to showcase the diverse flora of the region. In addition to community-based activities, scientific monitoring was also a focal point of the Setcases pilot. Three long-term biodiversity monitoring stations were established in distinct habitats to assess the presence and conservation status of vascular plants and bryophytes. Moreover, a targeted survey was conducted across 21 localities within Setcases, focusing on 10 specific plant taxa of conservation concern. The pilot initiative in Setcases has underscored the importance of integrating scientific research with community engagement to foster a deeper appreciation for local biodiversity. The village also actively participated in the Festi'Flora 2021, offering the public various intergenerational activities dedicated to the flora.

In this new phase of the project, Floralab+ is working intensively on the final development and formal establishment of the *Pyrenees Botanical Villages*, for the moment, doing the interviews mentioned. Some of the conclusions extracted from these interviews are that most of the villages are already carrying out actions, and this label can therefore help them highlight these actions and support them in going further. Also, we have discovered that the first actions the municipalities wish to implement are more focused on raising awareness, such as botanical trails. This label could therefore help support and guide them, through the different levels of certification, from awareness to conservation. On the other hand, the municipalities interested in this label are mainly those located within protected natural areas, which therefore are already carrying out many actions. In contrast, municipalities outside these protected areas carry out few actions for the flora due to a lack of resources and expertise. However, they are not opposed to leading initiatives if they receive technical support and assistance. Elected officials of the villages emphasize that this label can bring a sense of pride and recognition to the municipality, both from external visitors and residents. It can also enhance its attractiveness and thus generate economic added value.

Conclusion

All the partners are and will work hard to move forward with the creation of the label and recognize the important paper of villages and towns with the conservation of botanical richness and diversity, and above all its dissemination to the local people. What gives us

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures:

Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

confidence is the strength and reliability of our network of partners. Their continued support, expertise, and shared commitment to our mission play a crucial role in moving us forward. Thanks to this solid and collaborative foundation, we are optimistic that the desired outcomes will be reached soon.

Acknowledgments

Floralab+ is 65% co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER) within the framework of the Interreg VI-A Spain-France-Andorra Programme (POCTEFA 2021-2027). Andorra Recerca + Innovació thanks the Govern d'Andorra for the support received in the Andorran complementary call for projects Poctefa 2023, Ref. AUEP020-1/2023.

References

1. Andorra Living Lab. (n.d.). Andorra Living Lab. Andorra Research + Innovation. Retrieved May 13, 2025, from <https://andorralivinglab.ad/>
2. Collectif. (2023). Document de candidature du projet Floralab+ (2024-2026) au programme POCTEFA (2021-2027). [Report]. 85p.
3. Gascó, M. (2017). Living labs: Implementing open innovation in the public sector. *Government Information Quarterly*, 34(1), 90–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2016.09.003>
4. Gómez, D., García, M.B., Font Castell, X., Aizpuru Oiarbide, I. (2017). Distribución espacial y análisis ambiental de la flora vascular de los Pirineos. *Pirineos*, 172, e028. <http://doi.org/10.3989/pirineos.2017.172003>
5. Leitão-Barboza, M. S., Kawa, N. C., Junqueira, A. B., & Oyuela-Caycedo, A. (2021). Open air laboratories: Amazonian home gardens as sites of experimentation, collaboration, and negotiation across time. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 62, 101302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2021.101302>
6. POCTEFA. (n.d.). INTERREG VI-A Spain-France-Andorra Programme (POCTEFA) 2021–2027. Retrieved May 13, 2025, from <https://www.poctefa.eu/>
7. Tenas, B., & Oliver, X. (2022). Programa de certificació de poble botànic del Pirineu. ICHN Delegació de la Garrotxa.
8. Veeckman, C., & Temmerman, L. (2021). Urban living labs and citizen science: From innovation and science towards policy impacts. *Sustainability*, 13(2), 526. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020526>